

MANAGEMENT OF THE SPECIAL LABOR EXCHANGE (BKK) AT SMK BHAKTI NANTARA 666 IN INCREASING THE ABSORPTION OF GRADUATES IN THE WORLD OF WORK

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Abstract

This study aims to obtain an overview of the management of the Special Employment Exchange (BKK) in increasing the absorption of graduates in terms of planning, organizing, implementing, and evaluating. The research method used is qualitative method. This research uses a case study method which is one type of descriptive qualitative research. The results of this study are that SMK Bhakti Nusantara 666 in BKK management identifies the needs of the growing labor market and adjusts programs and services appropriately to increase the absorption of graduates, conducts effective communication strategies to promote the skills and competencies of graduates to potential recruiters. In the BKK Management Evaluation Process, cooperation with the Manpower Office requests data from schools on the extent to which graduates of SMK Bhakti Nusantara 666 are already working. The Manpower Office provides debriefing for students. At the end of the year SMK Bhakti Nusantara 666 evaluates the annual program to what extent the program has been realized. This evaluation is carried out by the public relations department at the end of each year. To overcome the interest of students and parents, SMK Bhakti Nusantara 666 invites the industry to explain and provide an overview to parents of students how their children will work, bring in alumni who have been successful as motivators to change the perspective that SMK graduates can also achieve success and provide work materials.

Keywords: BKK, Graduates, SMK Bhakti Nusantara 666.

INTRODUCTION

The importance of quality education as the main foundation of a country's development is undeniable. Effective education is able to produce individuals with the necessary capacity, knowledge and skills both for continuing education and for entering the workforce. One form of formal education that prioritizes the skills aspect is vocational secondary education. The main focus of this education is to prepare graduates who are ready to enter the workforce with the appropriate skills.

SMK is one of the vocational education institutions that aims to prepare students with relevant skills to directly enter the world of work after graduation. As economic growth and technological development continue to advance, the demand for a workforce with relevant skills and knowledge is also increasing. However, SMKs often face a number of challenges in preparing their graduates. One of the problems that often arises is the mismatch between the competencies taught in SMK and the needs of the world of work. This has led to low interest from the industry in SMK graduates. To overcome this, SMKs need to implement various effective strategies, including the establishment of Specialized Job Exchanges (BKK).

BKK functions as an intermediary between job seekers, especially SMK graduates, and parties who need labor from the world of work. Through BKK, SMKs can assist their graduates in finding jobs that are in accordance with their fields of expertise. The activity of sending workers from BKK to the world of work is an important part of efforts to increase the absorption of SMK graduates in the labor market. The success of BKK can be measured by the number of SMK graduates who successfully find jobs in accordance with their fields of expertise. Statistical data shows that the largest unemployment rate comes from SMK graduates. However, with the existence of BKK, it is expected that this unemployment rate can continue to decline along with the increasing employment opportunities for SMK graduates.

Research on BKK management in improving the absorption of graduates at SMK Bhakti Nusantara 666 in the world of work is an interesting topic that needs further research. The school, which is located at Jl Percobaan No.65 Cileunyi, Bandung Regency, has five competencies, namely Software and Game Development, Visual Communication Design, Animation, Accounting and Institutional Finance and Online Business and Marketing. The existence of SMK Bakti Nusantara 666 is supported by close cooperation with business and industry, both in the learning process and the placement of graduates. The learning process is not only limited to the classroom, but also involves direct practice in the industry through internship programs in related companies. In facing increasingly fierce global competition, it is important for us to prepare the mentality of students to compete well, which includes aspects of morals, independence, intelligence, as well as creativity and innovation in accordance with the times. SMK Bakti Nusantara 666 actively plays a role in building a learning society to face the new era, and strives to make its students a generation that is able to compete without losing their cultural and moral identity.

It is expected that with the BKK, graduates of SMK Bhakti Nusantara 666 can be more easily absorbed in the world of work according to their abilities and skills, and can help reduce the unemployment rate in the region. In the framework of research on BKK management at SMK Bhakti Nusantara 666, there are several aspects that need to be considered. First, this research can identify the role of BKK in facilitating the relationship between SMK graduates and the world of work. This includes the process of marketing graduates, sending workers, and aligning industry needs with the competencies of graduates. Secondly, the research can pay attention to the strategies and policies implemented by BKK in improving the absorption of graduates in the labor market. This includes efforts to empower graduates through soft skills training, increasing cooperation with industry, and developing effective job placement programs. In addition, research can also analyze the factors that influence the success of BKK in achieving its goals. These factors include support from the local government, the availability of qualified human resources within BKK, and cooperation with other related parties.

With a deeper understanding of BKK management at SMK Bhakti Nusantara 666, the results of this study are expected to make a significant contribution in improving the effectiveness of vocational education and reducing unemployment rates at the local and national levels. The findings of this study are also expected to be an important reference for other educational institutions in maximizing the role of BKK in preparing graduates to enter the world of work.

One indication of the success of BKK is the high number of SMK alumni who are successfully absorbed in the world of work. Based on this picture, the researcher is interested in further investigating the "**Management of the Special Work Exchange (BKK) at SMK Bhakti Nusantara 666 in Increasing the Absorption of Graduates in the World of Work**". With the existence of BKK, it is expected that graduates of SMK Bhakti Nusantara 666 can be more smoothly accepted in the world of work according to their capacity, skills, education, and aspirations, and can help reduce the unemployment rate in this country.

Based on information related to the role of BKK in channeling graduates, it is important to conduct a more in-depth study based on several previous studies regarding the role of BKK in facilitating the distribution of SMK graduates to the Business World / Industrial World. This article will discuss several issues related to the gap between the need for human resources and the difficulty of SMK graduates in finding employment. In addition, it is also important to highlight the relationship of the Special Work Exchange as a link between schools and the world of work. Therefore, it is necessary to improve the performance of the BKK so that the objectives of vocational education can be achieved.

Based on the formulation of the problem, the limitation of the problems that will be discussed in this study is related to BKK in increasing the absorption of graduates at SMK Bhakti Nusantara 666. The focus includes: BKK planning (socialization, determination of technical guidelines, program scheduling,); BKK organization (organizational structure, division of tasks); BKK implementation (program implementation); BKK evaluation (compliance with work programs, achievement of program objectives); as well as obstacles and solutions in the BKK process (inhibiting and supporting factors that affect the achievement of goals).

The general purpose of this study is to obtain an overview of BKK management in improving the absorption of graduates at SMK Bhakti Nusantara 666. The specific objectives are to understand the planning, organizing, implementing in the world of work, and evaluating the performance of BKK, as well as finding solutions to existing obstacles. Theoretically, this research is expected to contribute to the existing literature, become a reference for further research, and enrich insight into the performance of BKK in labor distribution. Practically, the results of this study can be reading material for students and academic staff at Universitas Islam Nusantara and become evaluation material for BKK at SMK Bhakti Nusantara 666 to improve its performance. Based on the description of the problem and background, the research questions raised are: how are the planning, organization, implementation, evaluation, and solutions to obstacles in the performance of BKK at SMK Bhakti Nusantara 666.

An organization needs effective management to achieve planned goals. According to Terry (2016, pp. 46-47 in Marifa 2020), planning involves selecting and combining facts with assumptions about the future to formulate the activities necessary to achieve desired results. Planning involves setting goals, strategies for achievement, implementing plans, and evaluating results (Boddy, 2008, p. 205 in Marifa, 2020) . Implementation, as described by Terry (2016: 138), involves efforts to encourage group members to carry out tasks in accordance with their respective roles. BKK carries out various activities, such as data collection of job seekers, tracking graduates, providing job information, offering graduates,

guidance, cooperation, placement of graduates, and fostering alumni. All of these programs must be carried out optimally so that the BKK objectives can be achieved efficiently and effectively.

RESEARCH METHODS

Research procedures are steps used as a tool to collect data and answer research questions.

1. Research Approach and Methodology

Research approach and methodology are two important aspects that form the foundation of the framework of a scientific study. Every study requires the selection of the right approach and appropriate methodology to produce data that is valid and relevant to the purpose of the study. In this context, a deep understanding of research approaches and methodologies is key to the success and efficacy of a scientific study.

a. Approach

The approach used in this research is a qualitative approach. Qualitative research is a research procedure that produces descriptive data in the form of written or spoken words from people and observable behavior (Moleong, 2006). The research to be conducted emphasizes the quality of the object rather than the quantity of the object (Fraenkel, Wallen, & Hyun, 2012). This research focuses more on trying to understand and interpret natural situations that occur based on verbal narratives and observations rather than using numbers in describing a phenomenon (McMillan, 2008).

The research conducted focuses attention with a variety of methods that include interpretative and naturalistic approaches to the subject of study (Denzin and Lincoln, 2009). Therefore, this research was conducted to conduct a study of a particular object, in this case related to the management of affirmation pathway PPDB naturally in order to form an understanding and interpretation of the phenomenon in terms of the meaning attached to it.

b. Research Methods

This research uses the case study method, which is one type of descriptive qualitative research. This method allows researchers to conduct an in-depth analysis of the case under study, such as problems, contexts, issues, and lessons learned. The case studied was the Management of the Special Employment Exchange (BKK) in Increasing the Absorption of Graduates at SMK Bhakti Nusantara 666 in the world of work, with the aim of producing new theories or adding to existing understanding. This research uses existing theories as a reference, and the results of the research can improve, complement, or perfect existing theories. The data collection methods used include archives, interviews, questionnaires, and observations.

2. Data Collection Techniques and Instruments

The case study research set as the research method to be conducted expects the use of diverse data sources. In line with this, the research techniques and instruments that will be used in this research can be explained as follows.

a. Observation

Yin (2011) notes that observation is a useful way to gain additional information about a research topic. Observation of a social or organizational environment can provide new dimensions to the understanding of the context and phenomena being studied. The purpose of using observation techniques is to observe the physical aspects of a particular situation as a source of additional information that can complement information from other sources. Observations are conducted to collect data needed to answer research questions. Observation is mainly used to monitor certain processes or conditions. The researcher makes two types of notes, namely a description that reflects the object of observation as accurately as possible, and the observer's analysis or comments on the description. With these two notes, researchers can obtain accurate and accountable data.

b. Interview

Interviews are used to obtain information that cannot be obtained through direct observation, such as thoughts, feelings, or past situations. In this study, the purpose of interviews was to collect data from principals or teachers. The interview questions were tailored to the research objectives and were conducted formally. Interviews were conducted naturally, without special preparation, and questions depended on the interviewer. Although they occurred naturally, data were still recorded or transcribed. The interview guide used was semi-structured, where only the outline of the questions was specified, leaving room for the interviewer's creativity and a more natural interview situation.

c. Documentation Study

Documentation studies are used by researchers to review existing written data. Through this documentation study, the researcher intends to build the validity of the data obtained both through interviews and observations. With the use of documentation techniques and records, it is hoped that more accurate research data will be obtained.

3. Location, Subject and Object of Research

a. Research Location

This research is located at SMK Bhakti Nusantara 666 which is located at Jl. Percobaan Cileunyi No.65, Cilenyi Kulon, Kec. Cileunyi, Kab. Bandung. The reason for choosing this research location is because SMK Bhakti Nusantara 666 has become a center of excellence school that has focused on the development of BKK. Has focused on implementing improvements in the quality of education in schools.

b. Research Subject

The subject of this research is basically a resource person who will be involved as a source of research data, namely the head of BKK SMK Bhakti Nusantara 666.

c. Object of Research

The focus of this study is on the efforts made by SMK Bhakti Nusantara 666 to increase the absorption of graduates in the world of work through BKK.

4. Research Procedure

a. Preparation Stage

In the preparation stage, researchers took several steps. First, they developed a research design, which was based on problems that could be observed and verified during the research. The second step was to determine the research location, taking into account its relevance to the research problem and aspects such as the quality and condition of the school.

After that, the researcher takes care of the necessary permits for the smooth running of the research activities, especially since the use of qualitative methods can affect the environment. The final step is to conduct a preliminary study, which involves field exploration and self-socialization. However, this step is not necessary in cases where one of the researchers is a teacher at the school.

b. Implementation Stage (Exploration)

The implementation stage of qualitative research is when data is collected in the field. Collection is done by meeting directly with the data source, with attention to creating a good relationship between the researcher and the data source. This is related to data collection techniques such as observation, interviews, and documentation.

When entering the field, the researcher adapts to the research environment, understands the research background, and adjusts appearance to local norms and culture. The researcher should be neutral, participate in activities, and maintain a close relationship with the subject. The duration of the study was based on information needs, and the researcher left the field after obtaining the necessary data to continue other research activities.

c. Final Stage (*Member Check*)

The data processing process began with data reduction, where data was organized in a detailed report or form. Then, the data is reduced, summarized, and focused on important aspects. Data that has been sorted and sorted based on concepts, themes, and categories provides a clearer picture of the observations and facilitates retrieval of data if needed. The next step is to organize the data, by grouping it based on the subject matter in the form of a matrix to make it easier to see the pattern of relationships between data.

After the data is categorized, it is analyzed using certain techniques, including the determination of special symbols, classification, and prediction.

The final step is to conclude and verify the processed data in accordance with the problem solving. After the process is complete, the researcher discusses the results of the study.

5. Data Processing / Data Analysis Techniques

The data analysis technique used in this research is using the steps as proposed by Bugin (2003: 70), which are as follows.

- a. Data collection is an important step in data analysis. The methods used in this research are interviews and documentation studies.
- b. Data reduction is the process of simplifying and transforming the rough data recorded in the field. This is done by summarizing, coding, tracing themes, creating data groups, and writing memos to weed out irrelevant information.
- c. Data presentation is a well-organized description of information to enable conclusions and actions to be drawn. Qualitative data is presented in narrative text and can also be in the form of matrices, diagrams, tables, or charts.
- d. Verification and confirmation of conclusions is the final step in data analysis. It involves interpreting the data to find meaning from the information presented. Qualitative data analysis is a continuous process involving data reduction, data presentation, and conclusion drawing. The data that has been analyzed is explained in the form of words to explain the facts in the field and answer the research questions. Each stage is carried out to ensure the validity of data from various sources.

6. Data Validity Assessment

In addition to the research stages as described above, what was done was an assessment of the validity of the data. This activity aims to increase the validity of the research results. This activity is carried out through procedures *credibility*, *transferability*, *dependability* and *conformability* as explained below.

a. Credibility (Internal Validity)

Credibility in qualitative research is important to ensure the validity of the research results. To increase credibility, researchers can carry out various activities such as increasing involvement in field activities, making continuous observations, using triangulation methods to check the truth of data by comparing it with other sources, involving peers in discussions to provide input and criticism, using other references to increase confidence in the data, and conducting membercheck to ensure the truth of the research results and make improvements if needed.

b. Transferability

That the research results obtained can be applied by the users of the research, this research reaches a high level if the readers of the report get a clear picture and understanding of the context and focus of the research.

c. Dependability and Conformability

This is done with an audit trail in the form of communication with the supervisor and with other experts in the field to discuss the problems encountered in the research related to the data that must be collected.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

SMK aims to prepare students to have character, master technology, be able to communicate well, and be competent in their fields to be successful in the world of work. According to the Department of Manpower and Transmigration (2001), BKK, which is a placement agency, was established to facilitate meetings between job seekers and labor users. BKK in SMK provides job delivery services to alumni with the aim of bringing job opportunities closer to available human resources, so that SMK graduates are easier to enter the world of work. The functions of BKK in SMK include providing employment information services, building cooperation with the government and the private sector, recruiting and selecting prospective workers, and assisting in the development of educational programs. BKK also collaborates with the Counseling Guidance (BK) in handling the career development of students and graduates.

The BKK implementation system consists of components such as legal basis, scope, accountability, program success, and organizational structure. The legal basis of BKK includes laws, presidential decrees, and cooperation agreements between educational institutions and the Ministry of Manpower and Transmigration. A clear legal basis ensures that BKK can carry out its activities in an organized and directed manner. The scope of BKK activities includes several aspects related to the organization, such as registration and data collection of job seekers, job vacancy search, career guidance, employment offers, employment delivery, verification, form making, cooperation with PJTKI, guidance for independent business, cooperation with related agencies, and provision of labor market information. BKK provides information to students and alumni about job vacancies, conducts recruitment and selection, provides guidance to prospective workers, and distributes graduates according to their talents, interests, and abilities. After distribution, BKK keeps in touch with the industry to conduct verification. In the process of guidance and counseling activities to prospective workers, BKK SMK Bhakti Nusantara 666 involves special staff. In the process of recruitment activities carried out by SMK Bhakti Nusantara 666, there are 2 processes, namely (1) Recruitment at school, namely when there are companies that need prospective workers, the school facilitates companies to recruit or select students. This recruitment activity is carried out according to needs, flexible when the company needs (2) Job pairs which are carried out once a year at the end of the semester. When recruiting graduates, prospective workers who will be recruited must bring Curriculum Vitae (CV).

1. BKK Management carried out by SMK Bhakti Nusantara 666 to increase the absorption of graduates in the world of work includes:

a. Planning

Planning involves (1) goal setting, (2) achievement strategies, (3) plan implementation, and (4) evaluation of results (Boddy, 2008, p. 205). At this planning stage, the Head of BKK SMK Bhakti Nusantara conducts program planning by conducting coordination meetings with the team starting in July. In the research at SMK Bhakti Nusantara 666, the idea of planning, which includes goal setting, achievement strategies, plan implementation, and evaluation of results, is in accordance with Boddy's (2008) suggestions. This planning stage is crucial because it is

the basis for all efficient management. In more detail, the steps at SMK Bhakti Nusantara 666 are as follows:

- (1) **Goal Setting:** The head of BKK at SMK Bhakti Nusantara sets clear program objectives, such as improving students' skills, opening up job opportunities after graduation, or improving the quality of education at the school.
- (2) **Achievement Strategy:** After setting goals, the next step is to design strategies to achieve them, such as developing a curriculum, collaborating with industries, providing skills training, or job placement programs.
- (3) **Plan Implementation:** The plan that has been created is then executed with concrete steps, such as organizing training, collaborating with external parties, or implementing extracurricular activities that support the set goals.
- (4) **Evaluation of Results:** The evaluation stage is conducted to evaluate the achievement of the set objectives. This may include collecting and analyzing data on student performance, feedback from industry or stakeholders, or exam results and other assessments.

By holding coordination meetings with the team since July, the Head of BKK SMK Bhakti Nusantara has started this planning stage by involving the entire team in the development of the program, ensuring that all members understand the objectives and are willing to commit to achieving them.

b. Organizing

To help facilitate the work process, BKK SMK Bhakti Nusantara 666 has an organizational structure, with the existence of this BKK organizational structure, it can be seen about the position of BKK administrators, job descriptions and responsibilities, as well as lines of authority and also the relationship between BKK administrators. BKK administrators or managers are determined and appointed directly by the Principal. All BKK administrators have their respective duties and responsibilities, namely:

- (1) **Head of BKK.** The task of the Head of BKK is to be responsible for planning, organizing, coordinating, directing and supervising the implementation of the procedure for the absorption of graduates in terms of recruitment of job seekers, selection and the results of the absorption of school graduates.
- (2) **Job Placement Officer.** The job placement officer is in charge of offering graduates to the business world/industrial world, receiving requests for prospective workers, establishing relationships with (DU / DI, Disnaker, P3MI) and releasing or sending prospective workers.
- (3) **Position guidance officer.** The position guidance officer is tasked with providing debriefing to prospective workers who will be sent both providing education and training in *soft skills* and *hard skills*.
- (4) **Registration Officer.** The registration officer is in charge of providing and facilitating registration services for prospective workers.

- (5) Information officer. The information officer is tasked with providing socialization related to job vacancy information and all BKK activities.

c. Implementation

At the implementation stage, there are several activities carried out by BKK SMK Bhakti Nusantara 666 including:

- (1) Socialization of BKK programs to 12th grade students, this activity aims to make prospective graduates aware of BKK work programs and services, according to the head of BKK at SMK Bhakti Nusantara 666 the process of socializing employment information to graduates is carried out by communicating via WhatsApp groups, Instagram. From there, employment information can be obtained by graduates of SMK Bhakti Nusantara 666.
- (2) Career guidance counseling is carried out to equip prospective graduates regarding readiness to enter the world of work. Prospective graduates will get guidance related to preparation for entering the world of work so that prospective graduates can know the *soft skills* and *hard skills* that must be prepared before entering the world of work.
- (3) Conducting visits / meetings with the Industrial World, this activity aims to obtain information related to job vacancies, training and internships, besides that with this visit it is hoped that further cooperation can be established so that an MOU is obtained with the industry, to strengthen the partnership SMK Bhakti Nusantara 666 also involves the industry in curriculum alignment, so that when graduating students are ready to work because they have skills according to industry needs.
- (4) Socialization of the Internship Program, this activity aims to provide information on the internship program so that prospective graduates get complete information regarding the internship program.
- (5) Providing competency development training, one of the BKK strategies in increasing the absorption of graduates in the labor market is by providing training to prospective graduates according to their competence, the training provided is BNSP standardized. After the training is complete, prospective graduates will get a certificate that will be useful for completing their portfolio when looking for work, besides that students at SMK Bhakti Nusantara when at the end before graduation will be equipped and trained on how to make a CV.
- (6) Holding a program to make AK 1 cards (job seeker cards) collectively in collaboration with the disnaker, this activity is carried out to make it easier for alumni and prospective graduates to meet the administrative requirements of job applications.
- (7) Entrepreneurial development activities in the form of entrepreneurship seminars aim to equip prospective graduates so that they can have entrepreneurial ideas and skills.
- (8) Alumni Gathering, this activity is carried out to pave the way for alumni management and build BKK cooperation with alumni.

- (9) Carrying out open recruitment (Jobfair) in collaboration with corporate agencies that have signed an MOU with the school, this activity aims to facilitate graduates to get direct employment.
- (10) During the distribution process, prospective graduates will be accompanied and provided with information related to the existing job market.

d. Controlling

Supervision is a very important activity in management, which according to Handoko (2003), is the process of finding and implementing the methods and tools needed to ensure that the plans that have been set can be implemented properly. In this context, supervision is defined as a process that involves implementing the work that has been carried out, assessing it, and if necessary, correcting the implementation so that it is in accordance with the previously prepared plan. Manulang (2008) explains that supervision is carried out by supervisors who are tasked with evaluating and, if necessary, correcting program implementation from the planning stage to implementation in the field.

At the end of the year, SMK Bhakti Nusantara 666 conducts an evaluation of its annual program to check the extent to which these programs have been achieved. This evaluation is carried out by the public relations department at the end of each year. One of the evaluation efforts carried out is through tracing alumni graduates (*Vocational Tracer*) and *Stakeholder Tracer Study* (parents and 2023 graduates). This aims to understand the extent to which BKK performance and school services have been successful in meeting the goals and needs of stakeholders. Thus, this evaluation becomes an important instrument in assessing the effectiveness of the program and provides valuable feedback for future program improvements. Supervision consists of evaluation and follow-up. The evaluation conducted by BKK uses administrative accountability reports per year, annual reports and resumes are prepared to evaluate all BKK activities. The report on the results of the implementation of BKK activities each year is made in the form of a written report and submitted to the City Social, Manpower and Transmigration Office.

2. Inhibiting Factors and Efforts to Overcome Obstacles in BKK Management of SMK Bhakti Nusantara 666

BKK management at SMK Bhakti Nusantara 666 faces a number of obstacles and challenges in absorbing graduates, which include:

1. **Diverse Student Interests:** Some students who enter SMK Bhakti Nusantara 666 have an interest not only in working, but also in continuing their education. This situation may hinder their motivation to learn.
2. **Influence of Parents' Mental Attitude:** Parents' mental attitude often restricts their children when there is a job opening far from home, thus affecting their decision in choosing a career.
3. **Students' Lack of Self-Confidence:** Some students may experience a lack of confidence in developing their competencies, which can affect their willingness to strive for success.

To overcome these obstacles, SMK Bhakti Nusantara 666 took concrete steps, among others:

1. Inviting Industry and Alumni: Inviting industry parties to provide parents with an understanding of future job prospects, as well as bringing in successful alumni as motivators, to change the mindset that success can be achieved from both college and vocational pathways. In addition, conduct briefing on work materials to increase students' understanding of the world of work.
2. Cooperation with counseling teachers: Through collaboration with guidance and counseling (BK) teachers, BKK management identifies students' interests and talents regarding their desire to continue their education or go straight to work. From there, they develop programs to ensure a balance between students who want to continue their education and those who want to work immediately.
3. Evaluation with the Manpower Office: In the evaluation process, BKK management works closely with the Manpower Office to obtain data on how many graduates of SMK Bhakti Nusantara 666 are already working. From this data, the Manpower Office provides additional debriefing to students to prepare them to enter the workforce.

3. Graduate Distribution Rate at SMK Bhakti Nusantara 666

Based on data obtained from the head of BKK, it was revealed that there are 80 companies that collaborate with SMK Bhakti Nusantara 666. Of the many companies, the majority have owners who are alumni of SMK Bhakti Nusantara 666. In fact, most of the employees in these companies are also the younger siblings of the owners. This is not only a form of appreciation for those who have contributed as alumni, but also an effort to strengthen social relations and increase cooperation between schools and alumni and companies.

Based on data from the head of BKK, it was revealed that in 2022, there were 76 graduates of SMK Bhakti Nusantara who managed to get a job through distribution from BKK, the highest number came from the Software Engineering (RPL) department, namely 31 people, followed by the Accounting department as many as 22 people, Visual Communication Design (DKV) department 12 people and Animation department 11 people. However, in 2023, there was a decrease in the number of graduates who managed to get a job through BKK, only 31 people with details of 2 Animation majors, 7 DKV majors, 11 Accounting majors and 11 RPL majors. This decline is caused by several reasons, one of which is the number of students of SMK Bhakti Nusantara who choose to continue their education to college. This shows that some students prefer to improve their educational qualifications by continuing their studies to a higher level rather than directly entering the workforce after graduating from SMK.

In addition to the factor of students choosing to continue their education to college, it is possible that several other factors also affect the decline in the number of graduates who work through BKK distribution in 2023. Some factors that may be the cause of the decline include:

- a. Labor market demand: Changes in labor market demand or unstable economic conditions can affect employment opportunities for SMK graduates. If there is a decrease in labor demand in certain industry sectors, the number of employment opportunities for SMK graduates may also decrease.
- b. Changes in education policy: Changes in education policy, either from the government or the school itself, such as an emphasis on developing certain skills or increasing access to tertiary education, may affect students' choice to continue their education.
- c. Competition with universities: The growing number of SMK graduates who choose to pursue higher education may be due to the increasing awareness of the importance of higher education in improving job opportunities and workforce qualifications.
- d. The role of parents: Parents' preferences for their children's education can also influence a student's decision to pursue higher education.

In the face of a decline in the number of graduates working through BKK, BKK management can conduct a thorough evaluation to identify the contributing factors and take strategic steps to increase the availability of employment for graduates of SMK Bhakti Nusantara 666. This could involve increasing cooperation with industry, improving skills acquisition programs, and providing information and support for students in making decisions about their careers.

4. BKK strategy of SMK Bhakti Nusantara 666 in increasing the absorption of graduates in the world of work

BKK management at SMK Bhakti Nusantara 666 conducts an effective communication strategy to promote the skills and competencies of graduates to potential recruiters through several strategic steps:

- a. Development of the READY TO WORK Application: BKK management created the READY TO WORK application that allows graduates to input information about their readiness to work. In this application, graduates can fill out their profiles, upload certificates

- and other supporting documents, and showcase their interests and skills to potential recruiters.
- b. **Promotion to Companies: READY TO WORK** applications are promoted to companies in need of manpower. This allows companies to see the profiles of graduates who are available and suitable for their needs.
 - c. **Identification of Labor Market Needs:** BKK management identifies the evolving needs of the labor market. They seek information on what companies need in terms of skills and competencies from SMK graduates. One way to do this is by obtaining information from graduates who are currently interning at certain companies. The information is then conveyed to the school to find out the number of graduates who are already working and how well their skills match the demands of the labor market.
 - d. **Collaboration with Industry:** BKK management collaborates with industries to understand more deeply the needs and trends of the job market. Through this collaboration, they can gain direct insight into the skills and competencies required by companies.
 - e. **Program and Service Development:** Based on information obtained from the identification of labor market needs and collaboration with industry, BKK management adapts their programs and services to ensure that graduates are equipped with skills that match labor market demands. This could be in the form of providing additional training, developing relevant curricula, or internship programs tailored to industry needs.
 - f. **Monitoring and Evaluation:** BKK management conducts regular monitoring and evaluation of the effectiveness of the communication strategies and programs that have been implemented. They measure the extent to which the programs are successful in increasing graduate absorption and improve or adjust the strategy if necessary.

By implementing these measures, the management of BKK SMK Bhakti Nusantara 666 seeks to ensure that their graduates have skills and competencies that are relevant to the demands of the job market, thereby increasing their chances of finding employment and succeeding in their future careers.

CONCLUSION

Quality education is the main foundation of a country's development, with a focus on vocational secondary education (SMK) which aims to prepare graduates who are ready to enter the world of work with appropriate skills. However, SMKs often face challenges in preparing their graduates, especially related to the mismatch between the competencies taught and the needs of the world of work, which results in low interest from the industrial world in SMK graduates. To overcome this problem, the establishment of a Specialized Job Exchange (BKK) is one of the strategies adopted by SMKs. BKK functions as an intermediary between job seekers, especially SMK graduates, and those who need labor from the world of work. Through BKK, SMKs can assist their graduates in finding jobs that are in accordance with their fields of expertise, with the hope of increasing the absorption of graduates in the labor market.

A qualitative approach was used to gain an in-depth understanding of the role of BKK in improving the absorption of graduates at SMK Bhakti Nusantara 666. The research method used is a case study, which allows in-depth analysis of the case under study. Data collection techniques include observation, interviews, and documentation studies. Data processing includes data reduction, data presentation, and conclusion verification. Data validity was assessed through several aspects, including credibility, transferability, dependability, and conformability. Overall, this study aims to provide a clearer picture of BKK management in improving the absorption of graduates at SMK Bhakti Nusantara 666 and make a significant contribution to the vocational education literature.

SMK has a comprehensive target in preparing students to succeed in the world of work. One way to do this is through placement agencies such as BKK, which is tasked with organizing meetings between job seekers and labor users. BKK in SMK provides job linkage services to alumni, helping them enter the workforce more easily. BKK's duties include various aspects such as providing employment information services, recruiting and selecting prospective workers, and assisting in the development of educational programs. With a clear legal basis, BKK can carry out its activities routinely and purposefully, while the scope of BKK activities includes registration of job seekers, job search, career guidance, and placement of graduates according to their potential and capacity.

BKK management at SMK Bhakti Nusantara 666 faces various obstacles in channeling graduates, such as variations in students' interests, the impact of parents' mental attitudes, and students' lack of self-confidence. To overcome these problems, they invite industry and alumni to provide insight to parents, establish partnerships with counseling teachers to find out students' interests and potentials, and collaborate with the Manpower Office in evaluating. In addition, they also implemented effective communication strategies, including the creation of the READY TO WORK application, promotion to companies, mapping of labor market needs, cooperation with industries, development of programs and services, and regular evaluation. With these measures, BKK SMK Bhakti Nusantara 666 seeks to increase the absorption of graduates and ensure that they are ready to compete in the job market.

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